

**THE ROLE OF DIALECT AND ACCENT IN MODERN FILM
ADAPTATIONS: A CASE STUDY OF THE GULLIVER'S TRAVELS**

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Annotation. *In this article we analyze the unparalleled role of dialect and accent in modern film adaptations, focusing on Gulliver's Travels. The research examines how pronunciation, regional accents, and dialectal variations are adapted for contemporary audiences. We compared Jonathan Swift's Gulliver's Travels with its cinematic adaptation and found that linguistic shifts in character speech and their pragmatic significance play a crucial role in audience perception. Using comparative, pragmatic, and phonetic analysis methods, it is determined not only how accents and dialects influence the audience's emotions but also their impact—both positive and negative—on social stratification and character identity. The findings reveal that filmmakers, while preserving the moral essence that the writer intended to convey, face challenges in adapting the beauty of language in a way that is accessible and engaging for young film enthusiasts.*

Keywords: *dialect, accent, film adaptation, Gulliver's Travels, speech variation, linguistic shift, phonetics, pragmatics.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается, как произношение, региональные акценты и диалектные вариации адаптируются для современной аудитории. Мы сравнили произведение «Путешествия Гулливера» Джонатана Свифта с его экранизацией и пришли к выводу, что лингвистические сдвиги в речи персонажей и их прагматическая значимость играют решающую роль. С помощью методов сравнительного, прагматического и фонетического анализа определяется не только то, как акценты и диалекты влияют на эмоции аудитории, но и их воздействие, как положительное, так и отрицательное, на социальную стратификацию и идентичность персонажей.*

Ключевые слова: *диалект, акцент, экранизация, «Путешествия Гулливера», речевая вариативность, фонетика, прагматика.*

The process of adapting masterfully written classic works into films requires linguistic modifications to ensure that young viewers can easily understand and experience the spirit of the era. Some of the most significant changes, while staying true to the original intent of the author, involve dialect and accent. If used effectively, these elements not only shape the character's identity but also create a deeper emotional connection with young audiences.

Although studies by Trudgill (2000) and Crystal (2003) have examined the role of dialect and accent in literature and media, there has been limited research on how these elements are adapted in modern film versions of classical works. My research aims to fill this gap by analyzing how linguistic features from *Gulliver's Travels* (1726) have been adapted in *The Adventures of Gulliver* (2010) for young film enthusiasts. This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How do filmmakers modify dialect and accent accurately without deviating from the original meaning?
2. What are the pragmatic and sociolinguistic effects of these changes on young viewers?
3. How does this adaptation influence the engagement and interest of young film audiences?

Methods

In this research, we analyzed Jonathan Swift's novel *Gulliver's Travels* and Rob Letterman's 2010 film adaptation using phonetic, pragmatic, and comparative analysis methods. Additionally, we transcribed key dialogues from the film and compared them with corresponding passages in the novel. The analysis focuses on three main aspects:

- Significant pronunciation differences between the novel and the film.
- Dialectal variations and their sociolinguistic significance.
- The impact of pragmatic adaptation techniques on character speech.

One can observe several examples from Jonathan Swift's *Gulliver's Travels* in the adaptation process of the film:

*"I replied that I was a poor Yahoo, banished from my own country, and that my only desire was to be admitted to live among these noble Houyhnhnms, in whose countenances I beheld a singular mixture of wisdom and benevolence."*¹

¹ This quote is from Part IV, Chapter IX of *Gulliver's Travels*
In traditional editions, this section is located near the end of the book, pages 240-241
(gutenberg.org)

This analysis indicates that archaic vocabulary has been masterfully used in this sentence: *Yahoo, banished, noble Houyhnhnms, beheld, singular mixture.*

Additionally, formal and elaborate stylistic elements can also be observed. From a syntactic perspective, the sentence is complex, with multiple subordinate clauses skillfully incorporated.

The transformation of the archaic words into modern words in the film dialogues:

Note: The examples below are based on the 2010 film adaptation of Gulliver's Travels.

*"I got lost, and I just want to stay here. You guys seem really smart and kind!"*²

From the analysis, it can be observed that the simplified sentence is used elegantly: the phrase *I got lost* has been transformed into a more audience-friendly version, replacing the literary expression *I was a poor Yahoo, banished*. Archaic structures have been easily omitted. Despite being an informal phrase, *"You guys"* is skillfully used as a hook to attract younger audiences, much like bait for fish.

In the book, you can see that Gulliver speaks Middle-Class British English, meaning his pronunciation aligns with Received Pronunciation (RP) or Standard British English. However, in the film, the opposite can be observed. In some versions, Gulliver speaks with an Americanized pronunciation. For example, the word *"can't"* is pronounced as [kænt] (American English) instead of [kɑ:nt] (British English). This approach is intended to make the film more accessible and understandable to an international audience.

Let's focus on an example from the book:

*"Your Excellency must be weary after such a perilous journey. We are honored to welcome you to our humble city."*³

Let's focus on an example from the film:

*"Wow, you're HUGE! Where did you come from?"*⁴

Let's examine one of the key differences: In the book, the Lilliputians speak in a highly formal and grand tone, whereas in the film, the opposite can be observed—their speech is casual and exaggerated, which becomes immediately noticeable. When *"Your*

² This scene takes place at the 15-17 minute mark of the film

Gulliver arrives in Lilliput and meets the tiny inhabitants for the first time

³ This quote is from Part I, Chapter II of *Gulliver's Travels*.

In traditional editions, this section appears near the beginning, pages 20-21.

the Global Grey eBooks edition. (globalgreyebooks.com)

⁴ This scene occurs around 17-18 minutes into the film.

The Lilliputians, upon seeing Gulliver for the first time, react with surprise and excitement

Excellency" is replaced with *"Wow"*, the added informality and humor make it as delightful to young moviegoers as chocolate.

The following table highlights major differences in vocabulary between the book and the film.

Original Word (Book)	Film Equivalent	Explanation
<i>Banished (Exiled)</i>	<i>Lost</i>	The complex word is simplified
<i>Singular mixture (Unusual combination)</i>	<i>Smart and kind</i>	The formal structure is simplified
<i>Your Excellency (A formal title)</i>	<i>Wow</i>	Formal speech is replaced with casual language
<i>Weary (Exhausted)</i>	<i>Tired</i>	An archaic term is replaced with a modern alternative

Dialectal and Accent Variations in the Film vs. Novel

This beautiful work, written in the 18th century, is composed in British English, skillfully utilizing compound and complex sentences along with a rich formal vocabulary. The speech of the intelligent and knowledgeable European traveler, Gulliver, stands out for its elegant and sophisticated style. This can be observed in the following example:

"I cannot but conclude the bulk of your natives to be the most pernicious race of little odious vermin that nature ever suffered to crawl upon the surface of the earth."

While these complex expressions are brilliantly used to portray satire and humor, it is natural for young moviegoers to find them obscure and difficult to grasp. The undeniable fact is that today's younger generation prefers a simpler and more informal style. Taking these factors into account, the filmmakers aimed to make Gulliver's speech more straightforward and relatable. A vivid example of this can be seen in the 2010 film starring Jack Black.

"Dude, I'm like a giant! This is so cool!"

To make the film more understandable for everyone, the regional dialects of supporting characters have also been modified, as seen in the speech of the Lilliputians. They are portrayed in an exaggerated manner, emphasizing their pompous nature. On the other hand, the Brobdingnagians, who speak in a slow and deep voice, are depicted as symbols of wisdom, which can be clearly observed in their characterization.

The Role of Accent in Character Identity

Another element that captivates the audience is the accent. It is no secret that accents play a crucial role in shaping a character's identity, not only in the novel but also in the film. It is easy to recognize young moviegoers' attention to the character through the various accents used in the film.

- **Gulliver:** In the novel, Gulliver is portrayed as a well-mannered and educated English gentleman, expressing himself in a formal manner characteristic of the aristocrats of that era. However, in the film, he sometimes speaks with a British accent and sometimes with an American accent, shifting away from formality. Through a comedic approach, the use of informal expressions and phrases makes him appear more casual and appealing to the audience.
- **Lilliputians:** In the novel, the author aims to depict a hierarchical society by presenting their language as formal and strictly regulated. In the film, however, exaggerated dialectal features are incorporated, with variations ranging from a posh British accent to a hurried and anxious tone, further highlighting their nervous character.
- **Antagonists:** In modern cinema, giving villains and opposing characters an unusual accent is a common technique used to differentiate them from the main protagonist. This approach is intended to make the antagonists appear more intimidating through their distinct speech patterns. In some cases, antagonists in Lilliput or Brobdingnag are portrayed with rough and exaggerated voices, making them seem excessively ruthless and authoritarian.

Pragmatic and Social Class Representation

Accent and dialect, as essential elements in both the novel and its film adaptations, serve as linguistic tools for adapting to the social environment.

- Power and social status serve as crucial linguistic elements in the novel. Gulliver's fluent and refined speech reflects his high standing, while the diverse linguistic styles of the different nations he visits illustrate their unique cultural and societal traits. The Lilliputians' complex language and the Brobdingnagians' wise yet simple speech highlight the author's satirical critique of both political and social structures, artistically portraying them with vivid literary expression.
- To enhance humor and emotional impact, the speech patterns in the film are adapted into simple and easily digestible expressions for young movie enthusiasts. Adjusting the complex and formal 18th-century English into a more accessible form while staying true to the original meaning is the most effective approach. For example, in the novel, Gulliver says:

"I find myself much perplexed by the customs of this diminutive people."

In the film, you can see a simplified version:

“These little guys have some weird rules!”

Here, you can see that they have successfully emphasized making it understandable for the audience while preserving the satirical tone.

- The most important aspect is that the language of the work does not stray from its literary and historical essence, while replacing archaic words with the beauty of modern language. This approach serves as an excellent way to maintain the audience’s attention and establish a connection with young moviegoers through colloquial speech.

Results. Focusing on the research findings, the changes between the novel and the film primarily aim to enhance audience engagement and make the satirical elements, which might be difficult to grasp in the text, more accessible through cinematic adaptation. The results suggest that for works written using the iceberg technique, filmmakers emphasize conveying the deeper meaning to young audiences through humorous scenes. Additionally, they highlight societal changes to increase awareness and prepare viewers for potential future challenges.

Discussion/ Focusing on the results, accent and dialect modifications in film adaptations serve several purposes. Firstly, they help simplify historically outdated words, making them clearer and more accessible. Secondly, they transform satirical passages that may be difficult to understand into more engaging and audience-friendly depictions. Thirdly, they play a crucial role in shaping the character’s image in the viewer’s mind. These findings can be considered a continuation of the in-depth linguistic research conducted by scholars such as Coupland (2007) and Lippi-Green (2012). Future studies may explore how young audiences perceive linguistic modifications in classic literary adaptations through empirical surveys or experimental research.

Conclusion. This study not only highlights the importance of accent and dialect modifications in film adaptations but also demonstrates how altering linguistic elements helps young movie enthusiasts quickly and easily grasp the deeper meaning of classic works. Future research could further explore how complex literary techniques, such as the iceberg method or satire, influence young audiences’ engagement and interest in films.

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